

DEVELOPMENT TECHNOLOGIES OF CROSS CULTURAL COMPETENCE

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Annotation: Teacher education needs to engage teacher candidates in developing cross-cultural competence so that they may be able to transmit global learning to their future students. This study theorizes cross-cultural competence (CCC) from the perspectives of multicultural and global education. A mixed- method design assessed students on CCC standards and found that they developed affective as well as cognitive CCC. By implication, the model can be adapted in other teacher education classrooms to foster cross-cultural, multicultural global learning.

Keywords: cross-cultural communication; language competence; method.

INTRODUCTION

As the world population exceeds seven billion, distances shrink, and people move in greater numbers across national borders, teacher educators are asked to prepare teachers who are competent in helping learners function in a globalizing reality. To this end, teachers are expected to possess the knowledge, dispositions, and skills to engage students with the globalizing world (and to do so in a transformative way). By transformative, in this context, we mean students making discoveries while experiencing a cross-cultural encounter rather than acquiring information “about” others in a predominantly cognitive and abstract way.

Scholars and organizations associated with teacher education agree that cross-cultural dispositions and change-agent skills needed by teachers for global learning cannot be gained abstractly: “Global citizenship cannot be achieved by merely learning

things in a traditional classroom experience, but rather requires active engagement with the world”. In the authors’ experience as instructors of core teacher education courses, however, socio-historical and socio-cultural knowledge of a multicultural globalizing world continues, despite transformative rhetoric, to be conveyed in traditional ways. Global learning is taught as an intellectual exercise, relying on course readings, for example, and has not been approached as a transformative exercise.

MAIN PART

Because of our experience, we challenged ourselves to develop a global learning project that would contribute to multicultural and cross-cultural global education in our core teacher education courses. We wanted to engage teacher candidates actively, both affectively and cognitively, in diversity and in interaction with others in global contexts by involving them in direct experiences, rather than learning “about” them. We also recognized the difficulty of evaluating the cross-cultural competence outcomes of teacher candidates in these kinds of projects. In campus-based teacher education programs like ours, creating situations to engage students in direct cross-cultural competence (CCC) experiences implies many obstacles: little diversity among students in classes, the short semester timeframe, and the inability of students to participate in study-abroad programs, due to work schedules and lack of resources.

Therefore, we proceeded in our core teacher education courses, over many terms, to develop and integrate experiential learning of CCC with the use of computer-mediated communication (CMC) Web 2.0 tools, including videoconferencing. We developed the approach in 10 sections of core teacher education courses over four years. Throughout this time, we explored how students manifested cultural competence and how it could be assessed². After reviewing the extensive literature across several disciplines, we formulated a set of standards of CCC to assess the teacher candidates’ performances. We used CCC standards in developing the instructional approach and the evaluation of learner outcomes, the cross-cultural competence approach (CCCA), which we explore in this study.

The significance of CCC for teacher candidates lies in its transgenerational

impact. The next generations of youth increasingly have to master critical 21st century skill sets which include global awareness and competence . It takes a cross-culturally competent teacher to diversify classroom experiences to include global dimensions and engage students in cross-cultural experiences . These authors postulate that, as teacher candidates progress through a reflective cross-cultural development process, they will experience a transformation of perspective from ethnocentric to ethno-relative and thus learn to guide their future students through similar processes.

As stated above, drawing from the multi-disciplinary literature reviewed, we developed the Four CCC Standards for assessing our teacher candidates from largely mono-cultural backgrounds. The standards used in our project follow.

CCC standard 1: Strengthened cultural consciousness and positive cultural identity development . This includes behaviors relating to the self, such as reflecting on one’s cultural influences and environments in order to understand own beliefs and values.

CCC standard 2: Positive intergroup contact and reduction of prejudice. This includes behaviors relating to the other, such as comparing values and beliefs, reconsidering one’s prejudices, expressing an interest to continue learning about others. Merrifield (2015) uses the term worldmindedness.

CCC standard 3: Acceptance, respect for and appreciation of the other who is culturally different from the self. This includes affective changes in behavior, such as gaining knowledge, insight, and understanding of cultural differences and accepting the world of the other, including “acknowledging the recognition or awareness on the part of the individual that he or she has a view of the world that is not universally shared” [3].

CCC standard 4: A perspective that is anti-racist, anti-sexist, anti- imperialist and pro-social justice action. This includes behaviors that signify a commitment to furthering intercultural contact and multicultural communities, gaining skills to negotiate cultural conflicts. Using their Global Perspectives Inventory, Braskamp, Braskamp, and Merrill (2010) found that most people who see themselves as global

citizens want to work for the rights of others. This standard directly addresses the change-agent skills that affirm voice and active democratic practices.

We recommend that teacher education programs incorporate, at minimum, online, synchronous video experiences in a variety of teacher education courses and that these be repeated several times over the course of a degree program. Any teacher education course, be it an intervention specialist or science methods course, can incorporate a discussion with individuals from dissimilar backgrounds about relevant topics in projects designed on the basis of the four CCC standards.

We identified two areas where further research would enhance effective CCC development projects. More action research is needed to ascertain what scaffolding in CCC project design is effective in enhancing flexibility in encounters with others.

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